

INVESTIGATION OF ASSERTIVENESS OF YOUNG WRESTLERS IN TERMS OF SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHICAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract:

The purpose of the present study is to determine assertiveness levels of young wrestlers in Ankara City in terms of socio demographical perspective. In this research, the Rathus Assertiveness Schedule was harnessed for data collection purpose. The research sampling is composed of 81 wrestlers from Ankara Şeker, MTA and Tedaş Sport Clubs. Whereas collected data was analyzed by the SPSS 20 software; normal distribution status of these data was examined through the "Kolmogorov-Smirnov" test; their homogeneity was examined through "Anova-Homogeneity of Variance" test. As a result, it was determined that collected data was homogeny and normally distributed. In analysis of data, descriptive statistic and one-way Anova variance analysis for determining the difference among the two or more variables were applied. Finally, it was found that assertiveness score of sportsmen with 4-5 years of sport experience was greater than the sportsmen in other groups; assertiveness score of 17 years-old wrestlers was greater than the ones from other age groups.

Keywords: assertiveness, wrestler, socio demographical

1. Introduction

This study essentially aims to investigate assertiveness levels of wrestlers in terms of socio demographical perspective. In both developing and developed countries, the basic problem of sportsmen is only thought to be fulfillment of their physical needs. Nevertheless, sportsmen are required to be taken as a whole and they are required to be given support and service in all relevant development areas. Similar to all other people, sportsmen interact with their surrounding in their social life continuously; communicate with other by affections and opinions. Hence, quality of this

communication is subject to social skills described as capability of acting appropriately to the current social environment. The relationship and communication types established by a sportsman with his/her society could directly influence on his sense of self and his/her harmony with the surrounding society. A sportsman capable of conveying his/her affection and thought to others while establishing communication with social surrounding minimizes experienced hitches and communication problems which would result in less compliance problem and accordingly this would be directly effective on his/her status in terms of experiencing psychological problem (1,2).

In general, it is reported that individuals react by adopting one of the four basic behavior types of submissive (shyness), offensive (aggressive), prompter (manipulative) and venturous in their social relationships (3). Of these behaviors, there are two types of behaviors which cause disconnection in inter-personal interaction: "*Aggressive and Submissive*". Aggressive individuals tend mostly to break others heart and humiliate then to acquire their targets. On the other hand, submissive individuals experience difficulty to reach their purposes and fulfill their needs. Therefore, they are full of sense of insufficiency or fury (4). On the contrary, assertiveness is reported as one of the healthy behavior types in establishing interpersonal communication and interaction (5).

Assertiveness is conceptualized as safe enterprise and self-confident behavior. This is way of expressing personal thoughts, affection and beliefs in an honest, direct way through appropriate means by observing others' rights in protection of personal rights. An assertive person effectively listens, discusses and builds up a passion in others to cooperate (6,7).

Additionally, if characteristics of assertive individuals are considered, it could be seen that they are capable of working independently from others; they behave openly and sincerely; they are optimistic and flexible; they enjoy life and fighting against life; encourage others and themselves; they participate in all aspects of life; they preferred direct and open communication; they embrace their personal issues, affection, senses and passions; they are tolerant towards social surrounding and hitches; they do not have physically significant health problems; they are self-confident and have self-respect (8).

Parents who are aware that assertiveness is a desired quality in interpersonal communication could direct their children to sport activities because it was reported in various studies that participation of individuals into sport activities develop their physical, moral and personality structure; and make significant contribution into strengthening self-control, facilitating team-work, establishing collaboration, developing self-confidence, freedom and respecting others and play significant role in being an assertive individual (9,10,11).

Additionally, studies conducted on both individuals participating sport activities and the ones do not, it was concluded that the persons attending sport activities were more vivacious, extrovert, hard worker, patient, ready to establish social relationship, conveniently to adjust a new status and more balanced in terms of sensually with respect to the ones who do not participate in sport activities (12).

Although various studies which indicate positive impact of assertiveness skill of individuals on interpersonal communication in the literature, no any study the relationship between this characteristic and status of adolescent basketball players and physical injuries in sport environment. The purpose of the present study is to investigate assertiveness levels of adolescent basketball players and to investigate its relationship with their physical injury status.

Assertiveness accepted as a social skill and described by Wolpe and Lazarus (1966) as *“sort of relationships form developed as way of protection of personal rights and expressing personal affection and thoughts without underestimating or ignoring others rights”* (13). Assertive persons are capable of expressing what they want in a clear and comprehensible manner. They display their positive or negative affections in a clear and appropriate language. They usually think positively about others and themselves. They use *“Me”* language. They are capable of establishing effective, healthy and coherent interaction. They are tolerant and sensitive in relationship. They cope with stress more effectively; they tend to speak about their successes and praise themselves when necessary (14). Some of individuals in society are submissive and aggressive; and some others have assertive social skill. Talent for establishing a healthy interpersonal relationship is perceived as social skill. *“Assertiveness”*, one of basic social skills, plays significant role in interpersonal relationships (15).

2. Method

2.1 Sampling

The universe of the study covers all young wrestlers in Ankara City. Sampling group of the study is composed of 81 volunteer wrestlers from the Ankara Şeker, MTA and Tedaş sport clubs.

2.2 Data Collection Tool

As a data collection tool of the study, Rathus Assertiveness Inventory was utilized. The reliability of the collected data was evaluated through the test and re-test method (78); and through split-half method (77). Voltan found in Turkish version that re-test method yield the result of 92; and that split-half method yield 63 and 77 reliability levels.

- 30.....80 Submissiveness
- 80.....130 Medium
- 130...180 Assertiveness (16)

2.3 Data Analysis

In data analysis process, the SPSS 20 package software was utilized. Whereas the "Kolmogorov-Smirnov" test was conducted in order to determine whether the collected data was normally distributed, "Anova-Homogeneity of Variances" test was utilized to examine homogeneity; it was concluded that collected data was homogeny and normally distributed. Afterwards of this initial examination, parametric test method was found appropriate for statistical analysis of the collected data. In this process, descriptive statistics and one-way variance analysis were employed. Additionally, Tukey test was used to compare variables.

3. Findings

This section includes analysis of collected data.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistic Findings According to the Age Variable

	Age	N	$\bar{x}$	$\pm$
Assertiveness	16	21	96,0476	14,01241
	17	40	96,2750	12,79420
	18	20	92,5500	17,67089

According to the descriptive statistic characteristics displayed by Table 1, it was determined while 17 years old sportsmen were ranked at the first place (96.0476 ± 12.794); 16 years old sportsmen were at the second place (96.0476 ± 14.012) and 18 years old sportsmen were at the third place (92.550 ± 17.670) based on their mean assertiveness score.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics Findings According to Sport Age Variable

	Sport Age	N	$\bar{x}$	$\pm$
Assertiveness	1-3	17	97,6471	15,96066
	4-5	17	100,1765	9,77391
	6-7	29	93,9655	15,01781
	8-10	18	90,6111	14,51222

According to the descriptive statistic findings displayed in Table 2, while sportsmen from the group of sport age 4-5 was ranked at the first place based on their mean assertiveness scores (100.176 ± 9.773); the ones from the group of sport age 1-3 were ranked at the second place (97.647 ± 15.960); the ones from the group of sport age 6-7 were at the third place (93.965 ± 15.017); and finally, from the ones from the group of sport age 8-10 were at the last place (90.611 ± 14.512).

Table 3: Descriptive Statistic Findings According to the Most Significant Achievement Variable

	The Most Significant Achievement	N	$\bar{x}$	$\pm$
Assertiveness	The First Three in District	26	98,192	14,280
	Championship in Turkey	7	103,714	8,577
	The First Three in Turkey	18	92,888	15,407
	The First Three in an International Competency	30	92,266	14,112

According to the descriptive statistic findings in Table 3, while sportsmen with Turkish championship were ranked at the first place based on their mean assertiveness score (103.714 ± 8.577); the ones with achievement of “*the first three in district*” were ranked at the second place (98.192 ± 14.280); the ones with “*the first three in Turkey*” were ranked at the third place with their mean scores (92.888 ± 15.407); finally, the ones with “*the first three in an international competency*” were ranked at the last place (92.266 ± 14.112).

Table 4: One-way Variance Analysis

Age Variable		Sport Age Variable		Achievement Variable	
F	P	F	P	F	P
.483	.619	1.565	.205	1.829	.149

According to Table 4, no any significant statistical difference was determined between assertiveness and variables ($p > 0.05$).

Table 5: Tukey Test Results Regarding Comparison of Variables

Age Variable	$\bar{x}$	$\pm$	P
16-17	96,0476-96,2750	3,88886	,998
16-18	96,0476-92,5500	3.12542	,719
17-18	96,2750-92,5500	3,95210	,615

Table 5: No any statistically significant difference was determined between assertiveness levels of sportsmen and age groups ($p > 0.05$).

Table 6: Tukey Test for Comparison of Sport Age Variables

Sport Age Variable	$\bar{x}$	$\pm$	P
1-3 and 4-5	97,6471-100,1765	4,86637	,954
1-3 and 6-7	97,6471-93,9655	4,35688	,831
1-3 and 8-10	97,6471-90,6111	4,79831	,463
4-5 and 6-7	100,1765-93,9655	4,33381	,483
4-5 and 8-10	100,1765-90,6111	4,79831	,199
6-7 and 8-10	93,9655-90,6111	4,25724	,860

As a result of comparisons of assertiveness level in terms of sport age variable in Table 8, no any statistically significant difference was determined among variables ($p>0.05$).

Table 7: Tukey Test for Comparison of Achievement Variables

The most significant achievement	$\bar{x}$	$\pm$	p
First three in district - Turkey Championship	98,192-103,714	6,01237	,795
First three in district - first three in Turkey	98,192-92,888		,613
First three in district - first three in an international competition	98,192-92,266	3,78330	,404
Turkish champion - first three in Turkey	103,714	6,28940	,320
Turkish champion - international competition	103,714-92,266	5,92674	,224
First three in Turkey - First three in an international competition	92,888-92,266	4,20967	,999

Table 7: According to the comparisons made between assertiveness levels of sportsmen and their achievement variable, no any statistically significant difference was determined among variables ($p>0.05$).

4. Discussion and Result

On the basis of descriptive statistic findings of wrestlers with regard to their “age variable”, it was determined that wrestlers aged 17 were more assertive in comparison with the other age groups. On the hand, wrestlers aged 18 were exhibiting less assertiveness behavior in comparison with other age groups. In the light of these findings, when it is evaluated according to the assertiveness scale, wrestlers aged 17 were more competent in communication in social environments with respect to other age groups; and it is possible to conclude that they express their positive opinions and thoughts in more clear and comprehensible language. On the contrary, it is possible to a conclusion that wrestlers aged 18 were experiencing difficulties in expressing their affections and thoughts in comparison with other age groups. As a result of comparison of assertiveness levels of sportsmen with regard to the age variable, n any statistically

significant difference was determined among variables. In the study of Gacar and Çoşkuner (17), it was reported that assertiveness levels of wrestlers from the age group of 16-17 assertiveness was 112; the respective value of the ones from the age group of 18 and older was found as 107. In another study conducted by Bayraktat (18), wrestlers from the age group of 21-25 were determined more assertive in comparison with the ones from other age groups. Voltan (19) concluded that assertiveness levels of wrestlers from the age group of 17–19 were higher than the other groups.

According to the descriptive statistic results regarding the relationship between sport age variable of wrestlers and their assertiveness levels, it was determined that assertiveness level of sportsmen from the group of sport age 4-5 was higher than the ones from the group of sport age 8-10. It is possible to conclude that sportsmen from the group of sport age 4-5 were establishing more effective and clear communication with their social surrounding; and they experienced less difficulty in their relationships with respect to other sportsmen. On the other hand, it was determined that sportsmen from the group of sport age 8-10 were experiencing communication problems with other individuals. As a result of comparison of assertiveness levels of sportsmen in terms of sport age variable, no any statistically significant difference was found among the variables. In the study of Bayraktat (18), assertiveness level of sportsmen from the group of sport age 1-3 was higher than the ones from the groups of sport age 4-6 and 7-10. On the basis of descriptive statistic regarding the relationship between the highest achievement of sportsmen and their assertiveness levels, it was determined that sportsmen who become champion in Turkey were more assertive with respect to other wrestlers. It was determined that wrestlers who were ranked in the first three positions in an international competition were ranked in the last places and their assertiveness characteristic was developed less in comparison with other sportsmen. It was determined that sportsmen who become champion in Turkey were able to establish more clear, positive and constructivist communications with their social surroundings; and they were able to express themselves in more clear and open language. It was also determined that sportsmen who were ranked in the first three positions in an international tournament were experiencing difficulty in their communication with their social surrounding; and as a result of comparison of assertiveness levels of sportsmen according to their achievement variable, no any statistically significant difference was determined among variables. In the study of Bayraktar and Yılmaz (20), assertiveness levels of wrestlers from the Turkish national team were greater than the ones from outside the national team. Alagül (21) reported a positive significant relationship between assertiveness level of sportsmen and their body perceptions.

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